

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some O,O-Diethyldithiophosphates/thiophosphates of 3-Substituted-5-mercapto-1,2,4-s-triazoles

B. N. GOSWAMI, J. C. S. KATAKY and J. N. BARUAH*

Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat-785 006

Manuscript received 2 March 1987, accepted 6 July 1987

A number of O,O-diethyl-dithiophosphate and -thiophosphate derivatives of 3-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-s-triazoles were synthesised by thiophosphorylation/phosphorylation of the corresponding mercapto-1,2,4-s-triazoles. The new synthetic compounds were screened for their fungitoxicity against *Curvularia verruciformis* (Agarwal and Sahl) and *Alternaria tenuis* (Nees). The compounds were also screened for their insecticidal activity against *Drosophila melanogaster* (Maigen). Most of the compounds exhibited high insecticidal activity.

BECAUSE of the less toxicity to mammals and easy biodegradability associated with the organophosphates they are widely used for controlling pests and these compounds have the property of anti-acetylcholine-esterase activity^{1,2}. In an attempt to synthesise organophosphorus compounds of biological potentiality, some O,O-diethyl-dithiophosphates and -thiophosphates (3a-i, 4a-g) of 3-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-s-triazoles were investigated and screened for their fungicidal activity against *C. verruciformis* and *A. tenuis* and insecticidal activity against *D. melanogaster*. Thiophosphorylation of the triazoles (1a-i) were carried out with O,O-diethylphosphorochloridothioate (2) in presence of a proton acceptor such as anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone. Sengupta and Garg³ obtained a single product during the synthesis of a number of O,O-diethyldithiophosphates of 3-aryloxymethyl-1,2,4-triazoles using the similar procedure. We could isolate a byproduct (5a-i) which was characterised to be ethyl thioether derivative of the mercaptotriazoles (1a-i) along with the expected product 3a-i (Scheme 1).

Structural elucidation of the thiophosphates (3a-i, 4a-g) was accomplished on the basis of elemental analysis, mass, pmr and ir spectroscopic data. The pmr spectra (CDCl₃) of the compounds 3a-i and 4a-g showed triplet in the range δ 1.45-1.60 integrating for six methyl protons.

Scheme 1

The methylene protons appeared as a pair of quartets at δ 4.32-4.50 due to coupling with phosphorus. In the case of the thioethers (5a-i), the methyl protons appeared as a triplet in the region δ 1.46-1.48 and the methylene protons appeared as a quartet at δ 4.28-4.45 ppm integrating for four protons. The mass spectra of the compounds showed exact molecular ion peak (M^+) and the fragmentation patterns were consistent with the proposed structures.

In the ir spectra (KBr), the frequency due to P=O stretch appeared in the region 1080-1020 cm^{-1} and that due to O-C stretch appeared near 1020-990 cm^{-1} . The band near 750 cm^{-1} was assignable to P=S bond of the thiophosphates. The characterisation data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Buchi oil-heated apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237B

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a-i AND 4a-g

Compd no.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula (M ⁺)	PMR δ ppm
3a	C ₂ H ₅	40	150	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂ P (474)	1.45 (6H, t), 4.32 (4H, dq), 6.9-7.9 (m, Ar-H)
3b	C ₂ H ₅ Br(p)	41	142	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ BrN ₂ S ₂ P (553)	1.48 (6H, t), 4.36 (4H, dq), 6.9-7.8 (m, Ar-H)
3c	C ₂ H ₄ Cl(p)	42	138	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂ P (50 ⁺)	1.40 (6H, t), 4.40 (4H, dq), 6.7-8.2 (m, Ar-H)
3d	C ₂ H ₄ Cl(o)	45	136	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂ P (508)	1.42 (6H, t), 4.38 (4H, dq), 6.8-8.0 (m, Ar-H)
3e	C ₂ H ₄ Cl(m)	43	131	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂ P (509)	1.41 (6H, t), 4.39 (4H, dq), 7.0-8.0 (m, Ar-H)
3f	C ₂ H ₄ (CH ₃)(o)	40	146	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂ P (488)	1.46 (6H, t), 4.38 (4H, dq), 7.0-8.1 (m, Ar-H)
3g	C ₂ H ₄ (CH ₃)(p)	42	154	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂ P (488)	1.46 (6H, t), 4.36 (4H, dq), 7.0-8.1 (m, Ar-H)
3h	C ₂ H ₄ (OCH ₃)(o)	39	126	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂ P (501)	1.52 (6H, t), 4.35 (4H, dq), 6.9-7.9 (m, Ar-H)
3i	C ₂ H ₄ (OCH ₃)(p)	41	131	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂ P (504)	1.56 (6H, t), 4.36 (4H, dq), 6.85-7.4 (m, Ar-H)
4a	C ₂ H ₅	38	Gummy solid	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ SP (457)	1.52 (6H, t), 4.40 (4H, dq), 6.8-7.8 (m, Ar-H)
4b	C ₂ H ₅ Br(p)	32	Gummy solid	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ BrN ₂ SP (537)	1.56 (6H, t), 4.38 (4H, dq), 6.82-8.00 (m, Ar-H)
4c	C ₂ H ₄ Cl(p)	30	Gummy solid	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ SP (492)	1.54 (6H, t), 4.30 (4H, dq), 6.84-8.12 (m, Ar-H)
4d	C ₂ H ₄ Cl(o)	33	Gummy solid	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ SP (492)	1.50 (6H, t), 4.38 (4H, dq), 6.9-7.9 (m, Ar-H)
4e	C ₂ H ₄ Cl(m)	36	Gummy solid	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ SP (492)	1.56 (6H, t), 4.30 (4H, dq), 6.85-7.90 (m, Ar-H)
4f	C ₂ H ₄ (CH ₃)(o)	30	Gummy solid	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ SP (471)	1.52 (6H, t), 4.32 (4H, dq), 6.9-7.2 (m, Ar-H)
4g	C ₂ H ₄ (CH ₃)(p)	37	Gummy solid	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ SP (471)	1.54 (6H, t), 4.36 (4H, dq), 6.8-7.1 (m, Ar-H)

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL AND INSECTICIDAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS 3a-i AND 4a-g

Compd. no.	Fungicidal activity		Insecticidal activity	
	Inhibition of conidial-germination (%)		Mortality <i>D. melanogaster</i>	
	<i>C. verruciformis</i>	<i>A. tenuis</i>	Mortality after 24 h (%)	LC ₅₀ × 10 ⁻⁵ mg
3a	81.79	22.75	100	1.640
3b	15.81	18.74	100	1.580
3c	5.20	7.80	100	1.630
3d	77.24	9.36	100	1.600
3e	100.00	100.00	100	0.015
3f	71.81	78.91	100	1.200
3g	100.00	100.00	—	—
3h	100.00	100.00	100	1.710
3i	100.00	100.00	100	0.018
4a	28.70	8.77	20	—
4b	—	—	—	—
4c	48.28	62.44	25	—
4d	—	—	—	—
4e	100.00	100.00	65	—
4f	100.00	100.00	78	—
4g	65.74	70.70	100	—

spectrophotometer, pmr spectra were taken at 60 MHz on a Varian T-60 spectrometer and at 90 MHz on a Varian EM-300X spectrometer using tetramethyl silane as internal standard, and mass spectra were recorded on a AEIMS-30 instrument at 70 eV.

In a typical experiment for the synthesis of the title compounds (4a-i), *O,O*-diethylphosphorochloridothioate (0.01 mol) was added to a mixture of the triazole (1a-i, 0.01 mol) in dry acetone (25 ml) and potassium carbonate (2 g). The mixture was refluxed for 3-4 h and then cooled to room tem-

perature and filtered. The filtrate after concentration to a small volume was chromatographed over silica gel and compounds 3a-i and 4a-i were isolated. The triazoles (1a-i) were prepared following the method³ reported earlier. For the synthesis of the thiophosphates (5a-g), *O,O*-diethylphosphorochloridate was used in place of *O,O*-diethylphosphorochloridothioate.

Biological activity: Compounds 3a-i and 4a-g were screened for their antifungal activity against 10-15 days old culture of *C. verruciformis* and *A.*

tenuis using the method of Horsfall and Rich⁴. In this method, the test compounds were dissolved in acetone (0.1%) and an aliquot (0.2 ml) was taken with a graduated syringe in microscopic grooved (15 mm × 3 mm deep) slides. The solvent was allowed to evaporate leaving a deposit of the test compound in the bottom of the depression and then the spore suspension (0.4 ml) was taken with a separate syringe. Suitable controls in sterilised distilled water were also used. The spore suspension was adjusted to give 40–50 conidia per low power field of the microscope. The slides were incubated in a moist chamber at 20–25° for a period of 24 h. The percentage of conidial inhibition was calculated by comparing the percentage germination of treated slides with the control. Average results of four replications are given in Table 2. Compounds 3e, 3g–i, 4e and 4f showed good fungicidal activities against both the test organisms.

The compounds were also screened for their insecticidal activity against adult *D. melanogaster* by residual-film-evaporation method. Dose depen-

dance studies were also carried out for some of the compounds and median lethal concentration values (LC₅₀) were established using probit analysis⁵.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Analytical Division of this laboratory for spectroscopic analysis, and are also thankful to Dr. S. C. Nath and Mr. P. R. Bhattacharyya of this laboratory for fungicidal and insecticidal screening of the compounds.

References

1. A. K. SENGUPTA and M. GARG, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **58**, 947.
2. R. CREMLYN, "Pesticides Preparation and Mode of Action", Wiley, New York, 1978, p. 80.
3. B. N. GOSWAMI, J. O. S. KATAKY and J. N. BARUAH, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1984, **21**, 1225.
4. J. C. HORSFALL and S. RICH, *Indian Phytopathol.*, 1953, **6**, 1.
5. D. J. FENNEY, "Probit Analysis", 2nd. ed., Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1952, p. 318.